

Working tribometer or AFM demonstrator made with LEGO™ pieces

Note: Due to time constraints, this design is not as fully developed or tested as the other demonstrators and does not have an accompanying parts list, or .csv file. A parts list is available on this demonstrator's Bricklink.com page.

Additional materials:

- strips of paper around 4 cm wide;
- paperclips;
- rubber bands;
- and a marker pen.

Optionally, you may need string or blu-tac.

Use

On a flat surface use a thin amount of blu-tac or double-sided tape to fix the model in place, if desired. Attach four rubber bands (two on each side) between the frame and the pen support. Like this:

Use more rubber bands, string or blu-tac to affix the pen in place on the pen support. Bend a paperclip so that it attaches to the pins on the paper winder and attach that to a paper strip. Like this:

To use, hook the paper onto the winder pins and pass the paper through the winder like so:

If the paper is attached to the pins correctly, when the motor is on, the paper will wind onto the top drum as the surface moves along. As the tip reacts to the surface, the pen (if properly positioned) will produce a force-trace similar to that of an atomic force microscope (AFM).

Tweaks

If you wish to tweak the model, simply download and install BrickLink.com's free design program [Studio](#). Then you can use this program to open the design file for this model:

“WorkingTribometerDemonstrator.io”.